

THE EDUCATIONAL IMPORTANCE OF USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL LESSONS

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ABSTRACT:

Teaching young children is not an easy matter. To achieve a goal, educators should be very careful to communicate with their pupils. The purpose of this article is to research the positive importance of the usage of pedagogical technologies in the teaching of elementary school as well as the use of new interactive methods in the lessons. Moreover, samples of interactive methods are recommended and illuminated.

KEYWORDS: reading, interactive, explanatory reading, intonation, method, teaching, expressive reading, art reading, elementary school.

Mother tongue, mathematics, reading, etiquette, science lessons in the educational system according to their essence, goals and tasks has a special place. After all, literacy and moral-educational education are in their land foundations. That is why students attend primary education classes special attention should be paid to increasing their interest. Because children are elementary they should not get tired of the sacred word "lesson" from the classes. Today's experienced teachers to increase students' interest in lessons they are using various didactic games. Interactive method - in the educational process interaction between teachers and students by increasing their activity under the influence of guaranteeing the assimilation of knowledge, the development of personal qualities The use of these methods helps to improve the quality and efficiency of the lesson will give. Its main criteria are informal debates and training freely expressing the material, independent reading, learning, conducting seminars, creating opportunities for students to take initiative, small group, large assignments, assignments, written works for working as a group, class team consists in execution and others.

Interactivity is the activity of two people, that is, the learning process as a mutual conversation in the form of a dialogue (computer communication) or the teacher - is based on students' interactions. Interactivity - mutual activity, action, affectivity, student-teacher, student-student conversations will be. The main goal of interactive methods is the most convenient environment for the learning

process and by creating a situation, the student's active, free, creative thinking, his need, to create an environment for the use of interests and internal capabilities. Such lessons it happens that in this process, not a single student was left out and heard, has the ability to clearly express what he has read, seen and known will be.

A process of mutual exchange of ideas is formed. Children have a desire to learn, interest increases, mutual friendly relations are formed. Interactive education heuristic (thinking, searching, finding) conversation through didactic games - by creating and solving a problem situation by designing a lesson process creative - based on creativity with the help of information and communication technologies includes methods of improvement.

Education on the basis of information and communication technologies, in turn, is a computer teaching using programs, distance teaching, teaching based on Internet networks, consists of media - educational methods. Age of students in primary education through didactic games according to their characteristics, literacy levels, and personal nature methods based on the design of heuristic conversations are widely used. In the process of teaching, if each student is at the level of his own learning ability he would have provided high quality and efficiency when working on assignments.

Such a situation can be realized only through differentiated education.

Now

we think about the implementation of educational processes through didactic games:

Interactive game methods to activate and accelerate student activity based on They are the realization of the student's creative potential and It is of great importance in identifying and implementing practical solutions for development have The main types of interactive games: intellectual (intelligent) and action and mixed consists of games. These are mental, physical, moral, spiritual, educational, psychological, aesthetic, artistic, entrepreneurship, creativity, work, professional skills helps to develop. In the process of education and training, students' motivations for learning, their reviewed the needs and services of the types of routes, based on a certain profession seen from a didactic perspective on interactivity is about Interactive games are theoretical, practical, physical, role-playing, work and others divided into types in the direction. They teach students to analyze, calculate, measure, make, test, restore, compare, correct, make independent decisions, working together in a group or independent team, developing speech, teaching new knowledge develops acquisition activity.

According to the theory of general games, there are all to classify the types of games according to their functional, thematic, constructive, didactic, sports and is divided into military games. Criteria for determining types of interactive games compliance will help well.

- according to the composition of the participants, i.e. boys games for boys, girls or mixed groups;
- by the number of participants - individually, in pairs, small group, large group, class team, interclass and mass games;
- thinking about the game process, thinking, thinking, based on actions, competition and others;
- according to the standard of time - the lesson, the part of the training time allocated according to the plan, games that continue until the goal of the game is reached and the winners are determined. All of this can be achieved by teaching students about interdisciplinarity to fully understand the scientific foundations of the structure and to form scientific worldviews, serves to develop creative thinking. Reading of primary grades classes have a special place in the educational system according to their essence, goals and tasks. Because the foundations of literacy and moral-educational education are based on it. That's why he imagines the education of other subjects without the education of reading it won't happen.

All in all, The student must first read the text correctly, quickly, understand it, and master its content are faced in all reading classes. State education of students through reading classes education and training, which is expected to be mastered according to the requirements of the standard (SES(Standards of education of the state)) the way is opened for them to acquire skills and knowledge. Just reading in education, the aspirations of a person, first of all, to understand himself, and secondly, the world, are encouraged. For this purpose, the "Reading Book" textbooks include mother nature, the world around us, the history and present image of our country, adults and children life, hard work, independence and national-spiritual values, friendship of peoples and It is intended to provide comprehensive understanding of various topics such as peace artistic, moral-educational, scientific-popular works are included. Reading lessons are literacy during the teaching period, introducing students to syllables, words and sentences and reading, if it is organized in the form of a story based on pictures, it is a reading technique after mastering, reading is carried out on selected artistic and popular scientific texts on certain topics.

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